

TEACHERS' LEADERSHIP STYLES: CORNERSTONE OF STUDENT DEVELOPMENT AND TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY

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ABSTRACT

This research study was undertaken to determine the significant relationship between the teachers' leadership styles, and student development and teachers self-efficacy. The descriptive method of research was employed in the study. A survey questionnaire was administered to 635 elementary teachers from selected schools of Second Congressional District of Quezon. It was found out that the teacher respondents perceived that the teachers' leadership styles are moderately practiced by the teachers. They considered that the student shows very satisfactory learning development. They also perceived that the teachers has moderate self-efficacy. It is divulged that the teachers' leadership styles has significant relationship to the student development obtaining the r-values significant to .01 level. Also, the teachers' leadership styles has significant relationship to teachers' self-efficacy having r-values significant to .01 level. Furthermore, the results also declared that the impact of the teachers' leadership styles to student development is explained by the adjusted R^2 of 19.2% of the variation among the teachers' leadership styles associated in the variation of student development. Likewise, the impact of the teachers' leadership styles to teachers' self-efficacy is explained by the adjusted R^2 of 21.1% of the variation among the teachers' leadership styles associated in the variation of teachers' self-efficacy. It is clearly revealed that the teachers' leadership styles has significant relationship with student development and teachers' self-efficacy having r-values significant to .01 level in all variables. It is realized that the level of student development is based on how frequent the teacher practice leadership styles in leading the learners, and the extent of teachers' self-efficacy is figure out on how frequent the teachers practice their leadership styles.

Keywords: Teachers, Leadership Styles, Student Development, Self-efficacy